

A Comparative Study of Prompting Strategies for Zero-Shot Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis.

Sebastian Småland

sebassm@stud.ntnu.no

Abstract

This project investigates how different prompting strategies influence the performance of Large Language Models on Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) in Norwegian public consultation texts. Using a hand-labeled dataset of 63 sentences, we evaluate three approaches: sentiment classification with a provided aspect term, zero-shot joint extraction, and few-shot joint extraction using in-context examples. The study quantifies how much performance degrades when the model must both identify aspects and classify sentiment under strict structural constraints. The findings provide a baseline for applying ABSA to Norwegian civic domains and inform future work toward fully automated extraction pipelines.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Digital public services generate increasing volumes of unstructured citizen feedback, making it harder for administrations to extract fine-grained insights that meaningfully inform policy decisions (Lindgren and Jansson, 2013). Municipalities such as Oslo face this challenge acutely: public-hearing processes routinely produce thousands of pages of citizen comments that must be read, interpreted, and summarised before decisions are made (Romberg and Escher, 2023). Manual analysis is resource-intensive and poorly suited to identifying *which specific aspects* of a proposal - such as density, traffic, or environmental impact - drive positive or negative reactions.

Aspect-level sentiment analysis methods have been effective for producing such structured insight across multiple domains (Liu et al., 2021). However, classical ABSA formulations often assume neatly annotated text or highly regular domains such as reviews, diverging from the complexity of public-hearing documents. Category-based sentiment analysis (ACSA) provides a more operationally realistic framing: instead of detecting all possible aspects, it evaluates sentiment over a predefined, policy-relevant set of categories. This aligns well with Oslo Municipality's AI Factory initiative, which aims to build reusable, scalable NLP components for decision support.

This project therefore treats ABSA as the conceptual task, while operationalizing evaluation using ACSA to better align with annotation reliability and municipal decision-support needs.

1.2 Problem

While Large Language Models (LLMs) offer a potential solution for automating this analysis, their reliability in specialized, non-English domains remains an open question. Standard "out-of-the-box" usage often fails to capture the structured nuance required for policy analysis. Therefore, it is critical to determine not just if LLMs can perform this task, but how they must be prompted to do so effectively. Specifically, we must understand the trade-offs between simple querying, structured extraction, and in-context learning when applied to the complex, formal register of Norwegian civic text; in this case public hearing documents within a municipality.

1.3 Goal

The aim of this project is to experimentally compare several prompting strategies for performing Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis in a zero-shot setting. By evaluating both sentiment-only and joint extraction–classification prompts, the study seeks to determine which prompt structures enable reliable ABSA performance in formal Norwegian civic text.

1.4 Contribution

This work contributes an empirical comparison of prompt designs for ABSA in Norwegian. Specifically, it provides (1) a controlled baseline that isolates sentiment reasoning, (2) an evaluation of zero-shot joint extraction under structural constraints, and (3) an assessment of how few-shot examples affect extraction accuracy. Together, these results offer practical guidance for designing LLM-based ABSA systems in low-resource, domain-specific settings.

1.5 Outline

Section 2 presents background on ABSA, ACSA, and prompting with LLMs. Section 3 reviews related work on prompt engineering and Norwegian-language NLP resources. Section 4 describes the dataset and prompting strategies, followed by experiments and results in Section 5, their implications in Section 6, and concluding remarks in Section 7.

2 Background

2.1 Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA)

Traditional Sentiment Analysis (SA) often falls short when a text contains multiple opinions. To address this, pioneering work by Hu and Liu (2004) introduced the concept of feature-based opinion mining, now commonly known as Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA). ABSA provides a more granular analysis by identifying specific topics (aspects) and the sentiment towards each. For instance, in the sentence, "The consistency of the pasta is great, but the saltiness ruins the taste," ABSA would identify a positive sentiment towards 'consistency' and a negative sentiment towards 'saltiness'. The task was later formalized and popularized through benchmark datasets in shared tasks like SemEval-2014 (Pontiki et al., 2014). Category-Based Sentiment Analysis (ACSA) is a constrained variant of ABSA in which sentiment is assigned to a predefined inventory of aspect categories rather than extracted freely from text. This formulation is useful in domains where relevant aspects are known in advance, making it well suited for public consultation data with policy-defined thematic categories.

2.2 Prompting Large Language Models

Unlike traditional machine learning models that require extensive task-specific training, Large Language Models (LLMs) can be guided to perform novel tasks through text-based instructions known as prompts.

In zero-shot prompting, the model is given an instruction without any examples, relying entirely on the knowledge acquired during its pre-training. In contrast, few-shot prompting includes a small number of examples of the task within the prompt itself. This provision of examples, called "in-context learning," demonstrates the model's powerful ability to adapt to various use cases, such as ABSA, by learning from the immediate context provided (Brown et al., 2020). However, despite its simplicity, the prompting is sensitive to phrasing, task framing and context structure. Varying these attributes will alter model performance, especially for tasks which require structure - like extraction based ABSA.

3 Related Work

3.1 Prompt Engineering for Information Extraction

Prompt design has become a central factor in LLM performance, especially for structured information extraction tasks. Foundational work demonstrated that LLMs can perform new tasks from a small number of examples embedded directly in the prompt (Brown et al., 2020). Subsequent research has shown that reasoning quality and extraction fidelity are sensitive to both prompt phrasing and task framing. For

example, Kojima et al. (2022) showed that explicitly requesting stepwise reasoning improves zero-shot inference, while Liu et al., 2021, Liu et al. (2021) demonstrated that selecting semantically similar exemplars improves few-shot stability. Recent studies in aspect-based sentiment extraction (Hellwig et al., 2025) underscore that even state-of-the-art models often struggle with boundary selection (i.e. the "exact word term") and structured output adherence, which is precisely the challenges examined in this work.

3.2 Advancements in Norwegian NLP

Applying these prompting techniques to Norwegian text requires accounting for language-specific resources. Work on NorBERT (Kutuzov et al., 2021) and NB-BERT (Kummervold et al., 2021) has shown substantial benefits on in-language pretraining for sentiment analysis and other NLU tasks. However, there is currently limited research on how instruction-based prompting performs for structured sentiment analysis in Norwegian civic or administrative documents. This motivates the present study, which investigates the reliability of zero-shot and few-shot prompting strategies as a foundation for future work on integrating Norwegian-specific pretraining.

Taken together, these findings indicate that while prompting techniques are powerful, their behavior on Norwegian civic text, especially for multi-label extraction tasks such as ABSA, remains insufficiently studied, providing the motivation for the present work

4 Methodology

4.1 Dataset

The evaluation dataset consists of 63 unique opinion-bearing sentences extracted from public consultation statements submitted to Oslo’s Agency for Planning and Building Services concerning urban development projects. Each sentence was annotated for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis using a predefined inventory of 12 domain-specific aspect categories: *Flooding/Water Management*, *Green Space*, *Land Use/Neighborhood Character*, *Light Pollution*, *Parking*, *Public Transport*, *Noise*, *Economics*, *Compliance*, *Social*, *Sunlight*, and *Pollution*.

To assess annotation reliability, an Intra-Annotator Agreement study was conducted. This method evaluates whether the same annotator applies the guidelines consistently over time, providing a measure of guideline clarity and task stability (Abercrombie et al., 2023). The 63 sentences were annotated twice by the primary author with a three-week interval, and Cohen’s Kappa (κ) was computed for each of the three labeling dimensions.

The analysis showed high internal consistency for the two categorical tasks:

- **Aspect category assignment:** $\kappa = 0.9351$ (“almost perfect” agreement; (Landis and Koch, 1977)).
- **Sentiment polarity:** $\kappa = 0.8752$ (“almost perfect”).

The span extraction task achieved $\kappa = 0.2132$, which is expected for fine-grained boundary annotation. Because the experimental evaluation focuses on *category–sentiment prediction* rather than exact span reproduction, the high agreement on the categorical tasks supports the dataset’s suitability as ground truth. Span boundary consistency is noted for future refinement but does not affect the core analyses.

4.2 Prompting Strategies

To evaluate how Large Language Models handle Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA), three prompting strategies were compared. Each targets a different capability: pure sentiment classification, full ABSA (extraction + classification), and few-shot guided extraction. The design follows an ablation logic: by removing the extraction requirement in Strategy **A**, we isolate sentiment reasoning from extraction-related errors in Strategies **B** and **C**.

4.2.1 Strategy A: Zero-Shot Sentiment Classification (Baseline)

This baseline assesses sentiment classification in isolation. The prompt provides the gold aspect term, and optionally the associated category. The model’s only task is to determine the sentiment toward that provided aspect. No extraction is required.

This setup establishes an upper bound for the performance of sentiment reasoning: any reduction in Strategies B and C can be attributed to difficulties in extraction, category selection, schema adherence, or interactions among these steps.

An example of a representative prompt is: “Based on the following text, what sentiment is expressed toward ‘[ASPECT TERM]’? Answer with Positive, Negative, or Neutral.”

4.2.2 Strategy B: Zero-Shot Joint Extraction and Classification (Structured Output)

In this strategy, the model performs the full ABSA pipeline without examples. The prompt instructs the model to:

1. identify all relevant aspect expressions in the sentence,
2. map each to one of the defined aspect categories,
3. determine the corresponding sentiment polarity, and
4. output results in a predefined JSON schema.

Since no examples or aspect terms are provided, this strategy tests the model’s zero-shot ability to follow multi-step instructions and generate structured, machine-readable output. Errors may arise from span detection, incorrect category mapping, sentiment misclassification, or structural schema violations.

4.2.3 Strategy C: Few-Shot Joint Extraction and Classification (In-Context Learning)

This strategy augments Strategy B by providing three annotated examples illustrating how aspect terms should be delimited, how category–sentiment pairs should be represented, and how the JSON output should be formatted. These demonstrations clarify extraction boundaries and reduce ambiguity in category selection.

Comparing Strategies C and B isolates the effect of in-context learning on stability in extraction, sentiment assignment, and structural adherence.

5 Experiments and Results

The aim of the experiments is to evaluate the trade-offs between output structure and model performance. The hypothesis is that few-shot prompting (Strategy C) improves extraction recall, while the rigid schema required in zero-shot structured prompting (Strategy B) may introduce reasoning or formatting errors relative to the sentiment-only baseline.

5.1 Experimental Setup

The experiments were conducted using *Gemini 2.5 Pro*, last updated June 2025 Google Developers (2025), accessed through Google AI Studio. Although temperature is often set to 0 for classification-oriented tasks to reduce sampling variance, the experiments follow the platform’s default setting of 1 to maintain consistency with common interactive usage.

The evaluation set contains **63 sentences** and **74 aspect annotations**. The aspects originate from public hearing documents labeled *Uttalelse* or *Kommentarer*.

Given the extraction difficulties noted earlier, *Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA)* is used to evaluate Strategies B and C. Rather than requiring exact replication of annotated aspect terms, ACSA measures whether the model correctly identifies the *aspect category–sentiment pairs* present in the sentence. This aligns the evaluation with the high intra-annotator agreement observed in the categorical labels.

The following metrics are reported:

- **(Strict) Triplet F1**: harmonic mean of precision and recall, based on triplet hits
- **Precision**: proportion of predicted category–sentiment pairs that are correct
- **Recall**: proportion of ground-truth pairs recovered on category level
- **Category-Sentiment F1** harmonic mean of precision and recall for a category
- **Sentiment Accuracy**: used only for Strategy A, measuring polarity correctness when the aspect term is given
- **Validity**: percentage of responses that were structurally usable (valid JSON or interpretable output)

5.2 Experimental Results

The performance of the three strategies is summarized in Table 1.

The results reveal a significant disparity between strict extraction and conceptual understanding. While Strategy **B** achieved a Strict F1 of only 0.1053, its ACSA F1 rose to 0.52634. This sharp divergence is expected: exact span matching penalizes semantically correct but syntactically varied extractions (e.g., extracting "*stø*" instead of "*mye stø*"), a difficulty foreshadowed by the low intra-annotator agreement for span boundaries ($\kappa = 0.21$). By relaxing the constraint to category-level matching, we observe that the model correctly identifies the underlying sentiment concepts significantly more often than it replicates the exact human-annotated phrasing.

The differences between Strategies **B** and **C** are modest, indicating that few-shot demonstrations offer only incremental improvements rather than substantial performance shifts.

Results:

Strategy	Triplet F1	ACSA F1	ACSA Prec.	ACSA Rec.	Sent. Acc.	Validity
A: Sentiment Only	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.8784	100%
B: Zero-Shot Structured	0.1053	0.5263	0.4639	0.6081	N/A	100%
C: Few-Shot (k=3)	0.0585	0.5380	0.4742	0.6216	N/A	100%

Table 1: Performance comparison across prompting strategies. Strategy A evaluates sentiment classification accuracy given a known aspect term. Strategies B and C evaluate end-to-end extraction of category–sentiment pairs (ACSA).

6 Evaluation and Discussion

The results highlight a clear separation between the model’s sentiment reasoning ability and its capacity to perform structured extraction. Strategy **A** establishes that Gemini 2.5 Pro can reliably classify sentiment when the target aspect is supplied, indicating that polarity detection is not the primary source of error in end-to-end ABSA tasks. Instead, the performance drop in Strategies **B** and **C** points to challenges in locating relevant aspect expressions and mapping them to the correct categories.

The relatively low precision in Strategy **B** reflects a tendency toward over-generation: the model sometimes identifies categories that are contextually adjacent but not supported by the annotated ground truth. This pattern is consistent with prior findings in instruction-based extraction tasks, where models attempt to satisfy structural constraints at the cost of semantic specificity. The introduction of few-shot examples in Strategy **C** reduces this behavior, leading to more stable extraction boundaries and slightly improved category selection. However, the modest size of the improvement suggests that demonstration-based prompting cannot fully compensate for ambiguous phrasing or compressed discourse typical of public consultation documents.

Recall remains higher than precision across both extraction strategies, indicating that the model captures most of the relevant category–sentiment pairs but struggles to avoid false positives. This trade-off is typical for instructions requiring exhaustive extraction.

The shift to Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA) provides a more reliable evaluation of extraction performance than term-level matching. Given the low span-level agreement in the ground truth annotations, this choice avoids penalizing the model for discrepancies that are, in practice, annotation ambiguities rather than model errors. The results therefore reflect the model’s underlying conceptual understanding rather than its ability to replicate exact textual boundaries. This is in line with (among other) findings by Hellwig et al. (2025).

7 Conclusion and Future Work

This study evaluated how large language models handle aspect-level sentiment analysis in Norwegian public-hearing documents, comparing sentiment-only classification, zero-shot structured extraction, and few-shot guided extraction. The results demonstrate a marked gap between the model’s strong sentiment reasoning ability and its weaker capability for end-to-end aspect extraction. When the relevant aspect is provided, the model reliably identifies sentiment; however, requiring it to detect and categorize aspects introduces most of the observed errors.

Adopting an Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA) evaluation proved crucial, as it aligns with both the annotation reliability and the operational needs of public administrations. The categorical perspective isolates the conceptual task: mapping sentiment to predefined policy-relevant themes, while avoiding penalties for span-level ambiguity inherent in public-hearing text. Few-shot prompting improves extraction stability but only marginally, suggesting that demonstrations reduce, but do not eliminate, the underlying difficulties of schema adherence and category disambiguation.

In general, the findings highlight that while LLMs can support sentiment reasoning in Norwegian civic text, their reliability in structured ABSA workflows remains limited without stronger guidance or additional supervision. Future work may explore integrating domain-specific fine-tuning, hybrid rule-based constraints, or Norwegian pre-trained encoders to strengthen extraction performance within municipal decision-support systems.

References

- Gavin Abercrombie, Verena Rieser, and Dirk Hovy. Consistency is key: Disentangling label variation in natural language processing with intra-annotator agreement. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.10684*, 2023.
- Tom Brown, Benjamin Mann, Nick Ryder, Melanie Subbiah, Jared D Kaplan, Prafulla Dhariwal, Arvind Neelakantan, Pranav Shyam, Girish Sastry, Amanda Askell, et al. Language models are few-shot learners. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 33:1877–1901, 2020.
- Google Developers. Gemini 2.5 pro model: Models overview. <https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs/models#gemini-2.5-pro>, 2025. Accessed: 2025-11-19.
- Nils Constantin Hellwig, Jakob Fehle, Udo Kruschwitz, and Christian Wolff. Do we still need human annotators? prompting large language models for aspect sentiment quad prediction, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.13044>.
- Minqing Hu and Bing Liu. Mining and summarizing customer reviews. In *Proceedings of the Tenth ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, KDD '04, page 168–177, New York, NY, USA, 2004. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 1581138881. doi:10.1145/1014052.1014073. URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/1014052.1014073>.
- Takeshi Kojima, Shixiang (Shane) Gu, Machel Reid, Yutaka Matsuo, and Yusuke Iwasawa. Large language models are zero-shot reasoners. In S. Koyejo, S. Mohamed, A. Agarwal, D. Belgrave, K. Cho, and A. Oh, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 35, pages 5–6. Curran Associates, Inc., 2022. URL https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2022/file/8bb0d291acd4acf06ef112099c16f326-Paper-Conference.pdf.
- Per E Kummervold, Javier de la Rosa, Freddy Wetjen, and Svein Arne Brygfeldt. Operationalizing a national digital library: The case for a norwegian transformer model, 2021. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.09617>.
- Andrey Kutuzov, Jeremy Barnes, Erik Velldal, Lilja Øvrelid, and Stephan Oepen. Large-scale contextualised language modelling for norwegian, 2021. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.06546>.
- J. Richard Landis and Gary G. Koch. The measurement of observer agreement for categorical data. *biometrics*, pages 159–174, 1977.
- Ida Lindgren and Gabriella Jansson. Electronic services in the public sector: A conceptual framework. *Government Information Quarterly*, 30(2):163–172, 2013. ISSN 0740-624X. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2012.10.005>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0740624X13000026>.
- Jiachang Liu, Dinghan Shen, Yizhe Zhang, Bill Dolan, Lawrence Carin, and Weizhu Chen. What makes good in-context examples for gpt-3?, 2021. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.06804>.
- Maria Pontiki, Dimitris Galanis, John Pavlopoulos, Harris Papageorgiou, Ion Androutsopoulos, and Suresh Manandhar. SemEval-2014 task 4: Aspect based sentiment analysis. In Preslav Nakov and Torsten Zesch, editors, *Proceedings of the 8th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation (SemEval 2014)*, pages 27–35, Dublin, Ireland, August 2014. Association for Computational Linguistics. doi:10.3115/v1/S14-2004. URL <https://aclanthology.org/S14-2004/>.
- Julia Romberg and Tobias Escher. Making sense of citizens' input through artificial intelligence: A review of methods for computational text analysis to support the evaluation of contributions in public participation. *Digital Government: Research and Practice*, 5, 06 2023. doi:10.1145/3603254.

A Prompts and Code

A.1 Strategy A Prompt Template

```
What is the sentiment towards "pen frste etasje" in the following sentence: Skanska er enig med forslagstiller i at frste etasje for bygg B br vre pen for bedre opplevelse av parken.
```

A.2 Strategy B Prompt Template

```
You are an expert AI assistant for analyzing Norwegian public hearing documents. Your task is to perform Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA).
```

```
Instructions:
```

1. Extract specific aspect terms. Focus on the core entity or noun phrase.
2. Consolidate multiple descriptors of the same entity into a single entry. Do not split adjectives into separate aspects. You can only use each category ONCE, to avoid duplicate entries of the same category.
3. Categorize each aspect into one of the following categories ONLY:
 - Flooding/Water Management
 - Green Space
 - Land Use/Neighborhood Character
 - Light Pollution
 - Parking
 - Public Transport
 - Noise
 - Economics
 - Compliance
 - Social
 - Sunlight
 - Pollution
4. Determine the sentiment for each aspect (Positive, Negative, or Neutral).
5. Output the result as a valid JSON list of objects.

```
Input Text:
```

```
"""
```

```
Skanska er enig med forslagstiller i at frste etasje for bygg B br vre pen for bedre opplevelse av parken.
```

```
"""
```

A.3 Strategy C Prompt Template

```
You are an expert AI assistant for analyzing Norwegian public hearing documents. Your task is to perform Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA).
```

```
Instructions:
```

1. Extract specific aspect terms. Focus on the core entity or noun phrase.
2. Consolidate multiple descriptors of the same entity into a single entry. Do not split adjectives into separate aspects. You can only use each category ONCE, to avoid duplicate entries of the same category.
3. Categorize each aspect into one of the following categories ONLY:
 - Flooding/Water Management
 - Green Space
 - Land Use/Neighborhood Character
 - Light Pollution
 - Parking
 - Public Transport
 - Noise
 - Economics
 - Compliance

- Social
- Sunlight
- Pollution

4. Determine the sentiment for each aspect (Positive, Negative, or Neutral).

5. Output the result as a valid JSON list of objects.

Examples:

Input: "REG er positive til at renovasjon inkluderes i planleggingsprosessen for utbedre trafikale forhold, og stiller seg til disposisjon for assistere med dette ved behov. "

```
Output: [
{ "aspect_term": "renovasjon", "aspect_category": "Compliance", "sentiment": "Positive" },
{ "aspect_term": "trafikale forhold", "aspect_category": "Public Transport", "sentiment": "Positive" }
]
```

Input: "Den foresltte hyden p 8 etasjer vil fre til mye skygge og er ikke tilpasset nabolagets karakter."

```
Output: [
{ "aspect_term": "hyden p 8 etasjer", "aspect_category": "Sunlight", "sentiment": "Negative" },
{ "aspect_term": "ikke tilpasset nabolagets karakter", "aspect_category": "Land Use/ Neighborhood Character", "sentiment": "Negative" }
]
```

Input: "Vi har ingen merknader til renovasjonslsningen, men stymessig er viftene p taket problematiske."

```
Output: [
{ "aspect_term": "renovasjonslsningen", "aspect_category": "Compliance", "sentiment": "Neutral" },
{ "aspect_term": "viftene p taket", "aspect_category": "Noise", "sentiment": "Negative" }
]
```

Input Text:

```
"""
Skanska er enig med forslagstiller i at frste etasje for bygg B br vre pen for bedre
opplevelse av parken.
"""
```

A.4 Evaluation Script (Cohen's Kappa)

```
1 import json
2
3
4 def normalize_sentiment(text):
5     """Standardizes sentiment to Title Case ('POSITIVE' -> 'Positive')"""
6     if not isinstance(text, str):
7         return ""
8     return text.strip().title()
9
10
11 def evaluate_absa(ground_truth_file, model_output_file):
12     """
13     Evaluates ABSA performance by comparing a model's output to a ground truth file.
14
15     Args:
16         ground_truth_file (str): Path to the ground truth JSON file.
17         model_output_file (str): Path to the model's output JSON file.
18     """
19     try:
20         with open(ground_truth_file, "r", encoding="utf-8") as f:
21             ground_truth_data = json.load(f)
22
23         with open(model_output_file, "r", encoding="utf-8") as f:
24             model_data = json.load(f)
```

```

25 except FileNotFoundError as e:
26     print(f"ERROR: Could not find file -> {e.filename}")
27     return
28 except json.JSONDecodeError as e:
29     print(
30         f"ERROR: Could not parse JSON in file. Check for formatting errors.
31         Details: {e}"
32     )
33     return
34
35 # For use in calculating totals
36 true_positives = 0
37 false_positives = 0
38 false_negatives = 0
39
40 print(
41     f"Comparing {len(ground_truth_data)} Ground Truth items vs
42     {len(model_data)} Model Outputs..."
43 )
44
45 num_items_to_compare = min(len(ground_truth_data), len(model_data))
46
47 if len(ground_truth_data) != len(model_data):
48     print(
49         f"Warning: Files have a different number of entries. Comparing the
50         first {num_items_to_compare} items."
51     )
52
53 for i in range(num_items_to_compare):
54     gt_item = ground_truth_data[i]
55     model_item = model_data[i]
56
57     gt_triplets = set()
58     for annotation in gt_item.get("output", []):
59         term = annotation.get("aspect_term", "").lower().strip()
60         cat = annotation.get("aspect_category", "").strip()
61         raw_sent = annotation.get("sentiment", annotation.get("sentiment:", ""))
62         sent = normalize_sentiment(raw_sent)
63
64         if term and cat and sent:
65             gt_triplets.add((term, cat, sent))
66
67 # 2. Get Sets of Triplets for Model Output
68 model_triplets = set()
69 for annotation in model_item.get("output", []):
70     term = annotation.get("aspect_term", "").lower().strip()
71     cat = annotation.get("aspect_category", "").strip()
72     raw_sent = annotation.get("sentiment", annotation.get("sentiment:", ""))
73     sent = normalize_sentiment(raw_sent)
74
75     if term and cat and sent:
76         model_triplets.add((term, cat, sent))
77
78 # 3. Calculate Metrics for this Sentence using set operations
79 tp = len(gt_triplets.intersection(model_triplets))
80 fp = len(model_triplets - gt_triplets)
81 fn = len(gt_triplets - model_triplets)
82
83 true_positives += tp
84 false_positives += fp
85 false_negatives += fn
86
87 # 4. Calculate after processing
88 print(f"\n--- Aggregate Results ---")
89 print(f"True Positives: {true_positives}")
90 print(f"False Positives: {false_positives} (Model predicted extra/wrong items)")
91 print(f"False Negatives: {false_negatives} (Model missed items)")
92
93 precision = (
94     true_positives / (true_positives + false_positives)

```

```

92     if (true_positives + false_positives) > 0
93     else 0
94 )
95 recall = (
96     true_positives / (true_positives + false_negatives)
97     if (true_positives + false_negatives) > 0
98     else 0
99 )
100 f1 = (
101     2 * (precision * recall) / (precision + recall)
102     if (precision + recall) > 0
103     else 0
104 )
105
106 print(f"\nPrecision: {precision:.4f}")
107 print(f"Recall:      {recall:.4f}")
108 print(f"F1-Score:   {f1:.4f}")
109
110 # Usage: first argument is GT, second is model output
111 evaluate_absa("output.json", "strategyC.json")
112

```

A.5 Annotation Guidelines

The following one-page guide was used to ensure consistency during the annotation process. It defines the scope, categories, and strict decision rules applied to resolve ambiguities.

Annotation Guidelines for ABSA of Norwegian Public Hearing Documents

Goal: Identify explicit mentions of urban/environmental aspects and their associated sentiments in citizen and organizational feedback.

1. Aspect Categories

- **Flooding/Water Management:** Issues related to rainfall, streams, drainage, and flood risk.
- **Green Space:** Parks, trees, gardens, and natural elements.
- **Land Use/Neighborhood Character:** Zoning, building purpose, height, volume, and aesthetic fit.
- **Light Pollution:** Excessive or disturbing artificial light.
- **Parking:** Availability, location, or necessity of parking spaces.
- **Public Transport:** Accessibility and quality of transit options.
- **Noise:** Sound levels from traffic, construction, or operations.
- **Economics:** Costs, property values, and financial viability.
- **Compliance:** Adherence to laws, regulations, and plans.
- **Social:** Aspects directly impacting human interaction or mental well-being (e.g., "trivsel").
- **Sunlight:** Access to natural light and shadowing effects.
- **Pollution:** Air quality, waste, and general environmental pollution.

2. Sentiment Labels

- **Positive:** Expresses approval, support, or beneficial quality.
- **Negative:** Expresses criticism, complaint, hazard, or undesirability.
- **Neutral:** Descriptive, factual, or procedural statement without evaluation.

3. Annotation Rules

1. **Explicit Only:** Annotate only aspects explicitly mentioned in the text. Skip implicit or speculative aspects.
2. **Minimal Phrase:** Select the minimal phrase that captures the evaluated entity (e.g., "mye lys", not "fører til mye lys").
3. **Categorization:** Assign the single most fitting category from the list.
4. **Social vs. Physical:** Physical buildings (e.g., schools, kindergartens) are categorized as *Land Use*, not *Social*, unless explicit social impact is described.
5. **Sentiment Default:** If a sentence describes a potentially negative object (e.g., "The plan includes a 28m tower") without using opinionated language, label it as **Neutral**.
6. **Granularity:** If a sentence has multiple aspects, annotate each separately.